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**TWENTY-THIRD INTERNATIONAL
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Optimization of 3D Printed Continuous Carbon Fiber Reinforced PETG Composites

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3D printing of continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CCFRCs)

Some limitations of 3D printed CCFRCs :

- Mechanical performances remain restricted by the fiber orientation within the printing layers
- Low strength of inter-layer bonding

➔ **Optimize the printing parameters to gain maximum mechanical performances**

What criteria should be considered?

- Maximize tensile strength in the fiber direction
- Improved inter-layer bonding strength

Composite fiber co-extrusion technology

What parameters need to be optimized?

Effect of nozzle temperature

- Variation in thermal history
- Improvement of flowability
- Enhanced impregnation of CCF in matrix PETG
- Improvement of molecular mobility facilitating interdiffusion across the interface

Effect of layer height

- Modified of carbon fiber content in 3D printed composite parts
- Variation in contact pressure between nozzle and deposited material
- Reduced interlayer voids
- Enhanced interlayer bonding

3D printing
of samples

Specimen for tensile test

Tensile test (ISO527)

Specimen for SBS test 18 x 6 x 3mm³

Short beam shear (SBS) test (ASTM D2344)

Analysis methods:

- ▶ Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine the significance of the studied parameters in order of influence on the mechanical performance.
- ▶ The response surface method (RSM) was used for the prediction of the mechanical performance as a continuous function of the studied parameters:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^N \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i \neq j} \beta_{ij} X_i X_j + \varepsilon$$

Run	Variables		Responses	
	$T_n(^{\circ}\text{C})$	$H(\text{mm})$	Tensile strength $\sigma(\text{MPa})$	ILSS (MPa)
1	220	0.36	412.61±4.41	22.78±1.24
2	240	0.36	413.44±12.83	24.15±0.23
3	260	0.36	435.82±4.09	26.47±0.53
4	220	0.4	381.45±18.59	22.71±0.51
5	240	0.4	391.70±4.34	23.21±0.60
6	260	0.4	408.07±8.29	24.95±0.35
7	220	0.5	324.84±6.33	20.41±0.23
8	240	0.5	330.21±7.91	20.70±1.06
9	260	0.5	377.50±20.05	21.25±0.87

RESULTS

Response surface of tensile strength

Response surface of ILSS

ANOVA for tensile strength

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	p-Value	Remark
$T_n(^{\circ}\text{C})$	2	6059.4	3029.7	12.61	0.004	Significant
$H(\text{mm})$	2	27063.2	13531.6	56.32	<0.001	Significant
$T_n \times H$	4	1101.1	275.3	1.15	0.367	Insignificant
Error	18	4324.7	240.3			
Total	26	38548.4				

ANOVA for ILSS

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	p-Value	Remark
$T_n(^{\circ}\text{C})$	2	39.953	19.9767	19.81	<0.001	Significant
$H(\text{mm})$	2	111.779	55.8895	55.41	<0.001	Significant
$T_n \times H$	4	10.643	2.6607	2.64	0.05	Insignificant
Error	36	36.311	1.0086			
Total	44	198.686				

Design of multi-response optimization

CONCLUSIONS

- The nozzle temperature and the layer height have a significant impact on the tensile strength and the interlaminar shear strength of the 3D printed continuous carbon fiber-reinforced PETG composites.
- Optimal range of values for the nozzle temperature, and the layer height were determined satisfying the requirements for the mechanical performances of the 3D printed composites using RSM.

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THANK YOU

Do you have any question ?

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